

MEASUREMENT OF THE LEVEL OF CYTOKINES IN RATS INFECTED WITH *ENTAMOEBIA HISTOLYTICA* AND THE THERAPEUTIC EFFECT OF GOLD NANOPARTICLES

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Abstract: This study was conducted on patients visiting Tikrit Teaching Hospital in Tikrit city and visiting some private laboratories in the Al-Alam district for the period from the beginning of January 2023 to the end of December 2023. 548 stools were collected and the percentage of infection with the amoeba *Entamoeba histolytica* was 29.92% for 164 samples positive for microscopic examination. The immunological study included the effect of infection with the amoeba parasite on some immune parameters of infected rats treated with different concentrations (0.4, 0.5) ml of gold nanoparticles. It was noted that there was a significant increase in infected rats treated with different concentrations of gold nanoparticles when compared with the control group at a probability level of $P \leq 0.01$ in interleukin-1, and a significant increase at a probability level of $P \leq 0.05$ in interleukin-17.

Keywords: *Entamoeba histolytica*, gold nanoparticles, Interleukin-1, Interleukin-17.

1-1. Introduction:

Entamoeba histolytica is an intestinal parasitic protozoan that causes amoebic dysentery in humans, which is a major cause of death and is responsible for approximately 100,000 deaths annually, as the number of people infected with the parasite is estimated at about 480 million infections worldwide. Despite its generally poor quantitative estimate, the impact of amoebiasis is still significant, and it is considered a prevalent disease, as estimates reach 40% in some population groups in some countries such as India and China (Nasar, 2024; Guillén, 2023). Amoebic dysentery is most prevalent in tropical and subtropical regions of the world and in developed countries, where it is common among travelers and new immigrants (Norman et al., 2020).

The life cycle of the *E. histolytica* parasite is simple, as its life cycle goes through two main stages: the trophozoite and the cyst. Infection with the parasite occurs by eating food and drink contaminated with the cyst in unsanitary conditions (Sharif & Raouf, 2022; Guillen, 2021). The stage that causes infection and causes damage to the host is the feeding stage, which lives in the cavity of the infected person's large intestine and feeds on the mucous membrane lining the intestine, damaging its cells, causing painful cup-shaped ulcers. This causes amoebic dysentery (ChIDEbElu & NwEzE, 2020). As for the clinical symptoms of infection with the disease, some people infected with the parasite do not show symptoms of the disease,

while others show symptoms of the disease, represented by abdominal pain, diarrhea, colitis, and the appearance of mucus and blood in the stool (Siciliano et al., 2020).

Gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) have optical and electrical properties that are different from those of conventional materials and have a bright future in medicine. These properties include stability, surface plasmon resonance, surface chemistry, multifunctionality, and high surface area-to-volume ratio. The size of AuNPs makes it easy for them to pass through cell membranes and affect cell permeability, protein synthesis, and metabolism, causing cell death in microbes (Alnuaimi, et al., 2023).

The *E. histolytica* parasite stimulates the host's cellular immune response when its infectious stage penetrates the host tissue. When it adheres to the epithelial cells lining the intestine, the host directs immune cells at the site of infection to attack the parasite. The host cell also releases nitric oxide and reactive oxygen species (ROS) to destroy the feeding stages, and also stimulates cells to produce and release cytokines. These cytokines are known to have a range of activity against the invading feeding stages. The humoral response is stimulated upon infection with the parasite by an increase in IgG, IgA, and IgM antibodies and an increase in CD4 and CD8 differentiation complexes (Singh & Banerjee, 2022; Loh et al., 2013).

IL-1 is involved in many physiological processes in mammals, including regulation of homeostasis, metabolism, stress signaling, tissue regeneration and repair, as well as regulation of infectious processes, immunity, and chronic sterile inflammation. Sterile inflammation refers to the activation of the immune system, which is not associated with pathogen invasion (Etti et al., 2018).

IL-17 functions in host defense against pathogens and plays various roles in inflammation in autoimmune conditions, allergies, and chronic inflammation (Monin & Gaffen., 2018).

2-Materials and methods:

2-1: Samples collection

Stool samples for *E. histolytica* were taken from patients who visited and were hospitalized at Tikrit Teaching Hospital and private laboratories in Al-Alam District, who were suffering from severe to moderate diarrhea, and most often those who had bloody diarrhea, during the period from 1/1/2023 to 30/12/2023. The samples were placed in sterile plastic bottles with a wide opening and a tight lid to maintain the moisture of the sample and prevent it from drying out. Microscopic examination of the samples was performed during the first half hour, taking care to take the sample from areas containing mucus or blood in search of the active stage responsible for infection with the parasite. The active stage is often observed in soft samples and is rarely observed in solid or semi-solid stool, which usually contains the cystic stage, and its presence often indicates infection with the parasite (Clark & Diamond, 2002).

2-2: Examination of stool samples

The samples were examined by the direct wet smear method used to diagnose the trophozoite stage to observe the movement of the amoebic dysentery parasite, which can be distinguished from the movement of other types of amoebae in that its movement is always directional. It is possible to observe the parasite cytoplasm containing red blood cells (R.B.C.). Especially in the samples of acute amoebic dysentery that were collected, the examination is done by taking a drop of physiological saline solution and placing it on one end of the glass slide and a drop of local iodine solution on the other end of the slide, and an amount of feces was taken the size of a match head from several places by means of a clean wooden stick, and the amount of feces taken was mixed with the physiological saline solution on the slide, and in the same way another amount of feces was taken and mixed with the local iodine solution until the mixture became homogeneous, and then the slide cover was placed and then examined with a light microscope with a 100X oil lens to confirm the presence of the parasite (Singh et al, 2009).

2-3: Parasite isolation

The parasite was isolated from stool samples obtained from patients with diarrhea, in which the presence of the parasite was proven by direct microscopic examination. The parasite cysts were concentrated by flotation with a saturated sugar solution prepared according to the method of (John & Petri, 2006), consisting of dissolving 500 g of sucrose powder in 1000 ml of distilled water, then 6.5 g of phenol was added to the solution. The method is done by mixing a certain weight of stool in 10 cm of distilled water, then the mixture was filtered through several layers of sterile medical gauze until impurities were removed. The filtrate was placed in glass tubes and placed in a centrifuge to be centrifuged at a speed of 2500 rpm for 10 minutes. The filtrate was then discarded and the precipitate was taken and 3 cm³ of distilled water was added to it and centrifuged at a speed of 2500 rpm for 10 minutes. The process was repeated until a completely clear suspension was obtained. Then the filtrate was discarded and the sediment was taken and an appropriate amount of saturated sugar solution was added to it until the tube was full and placed in the centrifuge at a speed of 500 rpm for 10 minutes. Then the upper layer was examined to calculate the number of bags given to the animal (Clark and Diamond, 2002).

2-4: gold nanoparticles

Gold nanoparticles (GNPs) were prepared by chemical synthesis, where citrate-coated gold nanoparticles (GNPs) with a diameter of 20 nm were prepared by reducing 1 mmol of H₂AuCl₄ with sodium citrate (1%) according to the method of (Herizchi et al., 2016; Leng et al., 2015) with slight modification as follows:

1. 1-10ml of H₂AuCl₄ was heated near boiling temperature.
2. Add 1 ml of citrate solution quickly.
3. The solution was stirred continuously with a magnetic stirrer, and the yellow color of gold ions faded to colorless. Then the sky blue color appeared and darkened to dark blue, and turned to cherry red after 15 minutes of heating.
4. The mixing continued until cooling to room temperature.
5. The dark red mixture was filtered with a 0.22 μmol membrane filter (Millipore), then the gold nanoparticles were stored in the refrigerator at 4°C until use.

2-5: Experimental animals

Male laboratory rats, 6-8 weeks old and weighing 120-180 grams, were used. They were taken from the animal house of the College of Veterinary Medicine / Tikrit University, after ensuring that they were free from apparent diseases and free from intestinal parasites. The animals were placed in clean plastic cages for raising laboratory animals. The animals were divided into four groups and placed in plastic cages, one cage for each group. All of them were in large cages equipped with special feeders and covered with a metal cover with a floor covered with sawdust. The animals were treated as follows:

1. The first group (negative control): includes (5 animals) and was given normal drinking water throughout the experiment period.
2. The second group: positive control includes (5 animals). The rats were orally dosed with 8000 cysts of histolytic amoeba and the stool of each rat was examined for a week until the infection appeared.
3. The third group: includes (5 animals) orally dosed with histolytic amoeba and the stool of the rats was examined daily for a week until the infection appeared, then they were orally dosed with gold nanoparticles at a concentration of 3.75 cm³ after infection for 10 days at a rate of 1 ml.

4. The fourth group: includes (5 animals) orally dosed with histolytic amoeba and the stool of the rats was examined daily for a week until the infection appeared, then they were orally dosed with gold nanoparticles at a concentration of 5 cm³ after infection for 10 days at a rate of 1 ml.

Laboratory rats were dosed with 8000 amoeba cysts orally using a gastric syringe, by inserting the syringe into the mouth, and pushing the liquid containing the parasite cysts. For a week after infection, the rats were placed in clean cages free of sawdust. The parasite cysts were investigated in the feces of infected animals to confirm the occurrence of parasite infection. The infection was confirmed by preparing several smears from the feces of infected rats on a glass slide and examining them under a microscope. The parasite and its different stages were observed. After confirming the infection of the animals, they were dosed with gold nanoparticles. The rats were dissected 10 days after treatment with gold nanoparticles, then examined to observe the pathological changes visually. The intestines and liver were taken and fixed in formalin solution, and preserved in it to study the histological changes during the infection period.

2-6: Collect Blood Samples

After the specified period of the experiment, the rats were killed after anesthetizing them with chloroform. Then, blood samples were drawn from the heart and placed in test tubes free of anticoagulant. They were left for approximately 15 minutes at 37°C. After that, the serum was obtained by centrifuging at 3000 rpm for 15 minutes. It was stored at -20°C in new, clean plastic tubes until the biochemical tests were performed, which included antioxidants (MDA, GSH) and liver enzymes (AST, ALT).

2-7: Immunological tests

Serum IL-1 and IL-17 Concentration Measurement: Using ELIZA technology using the kit supplied by Sunlong Biotech of China to measure IL-1 and IL-17 in Pg/ml units according to the manufacturer's instructions. A standard curve is drawn to extract the antibody values in rats infected with *Entamoeba histolytica* and the therapeutic effect of gold nanoparticles.

2-9: Statistical Analysis

The results were statistically analyzed using the (ANOVA) program, using the Chi-Square (Chi X²) test, at a probability level of ($P \geq 0.01$) and ($P \geq 0.05$) to determine the significant differences in infection with the parasite under study and its relationship to some biochemical parameters when compared with the control groups.

3-Results and discussion

3-1: Percentage of *E. histolytica* parasite in stool samples examined under a microscope:

Stool samples were collected from the laboratories of Tikrit Teaching Hospital and some private laboratories in Al-Alam District for both sexes for the period from January 2023 to December 2023. The *E. histolytica* parasite was diagnosed through microscopic examination of stool samples in only 164 samples out of 548 samples, at a percentage of 29.92% (Table 3-1).

Table (3-1): Percentage of samples positive for *E. histolytica*

Total number of samples tested	Number of infected samples	percentage
548	164	29.92%

This study recorded rates close to those recorded by (Anwar, 2014) in Kirkuk city, where the infection rate reached 30.22%, and what (Nassar et al., 2019) recorded in Basra Governorate, where the infection rate reached 32%. It also agrees with what (Al-Sumaidi, 2022) recorded in Tikrit, where the infection rate was 26.1%. And with what (Mohsin et al., 2022) recorded in Kirkuk, where the total infection rate with the *E.*

histolytica parasite reached 29.6%. While our results did not agree with what (Lazar, 2012) recorded, where the infection rate reached 21.67% in Kirkuk, and (Al-Yasiri, 2015) recorded in Nasiriyah a rate of 19.5%, and (Kadir et al., 2018) in Tikrit recorded an infection rate of 9.3%. What was recorded by (AL-Khikani et al., 2019) in Babylon, where the infection rate reached 17.91%, and ((Zangana & Erdeni ., 2020) recorded in Tikrit an infection rate of 13.375%, and with what was recorded by (Aziz et al., 2022) in Sulaymaniyah, he recorded an infection rate of 19.3%, and (Nayyef et al., 2022) recorded in Baghdad an infection rate of 15.89%.

The differences in the incidence of the parasite in this study and previous studies are due to differences in population density, sanitation, personal hygiene, geographical location, climatic conditions, number of samples examined, accuracy and skill of the examiner, educational level and age groups in the population studied. As for the similarity in the incidence rate, it may be due to similarity in cultural, health and social levels (Zangana & Erdeni, 2020).

3-2: Cytokines (Level of Interleukin-1 and interleukin-17)

The results showed a difference in the concentration rate of interleukin-1 and interleukin-17 in laboratory rats infected with a concentration of 0.4 and 0.5 ml with dysentery amoeba and treated with concentrations of 3.75 and 5 cm³ of gold nanoparticles, as an increase in the concentration rate of interleukin-1 was observed for the positive control group, reaching 182.66 pg/ml compared to the negative control group, which reached 150.50 pg/ml, and a decrease in the concentration rate of interleukin-1 was observed when using gold nanoparticles at a concentration of 3.75 and 5 cm³ for the infected groups.

It was also noted that there was an increase in the concentration rate of interleukin-17 for the positive control group, which reached 228.70 pg/ml, compared to the negative control group, which reached 204.30 pg/ml. It was also noted that there was a decrease in the concentration rate of interleukin-17 when using gold nanoparticles at a concentration of 3.75 and 5 cm³ for the infected groups. (Table 3-2).

Table (3-2): Average concentrations of cytokines IL-1 and IL-17 in laboratory rats infected with dysentery amoeba and treated with different concentrations of gold nanoparticles.

Groups Tests	Mean ± S.D	
	IL-1 Pg/ml	IL-17 Pg/ml
negative control	150.50±3.10	204.30±20.3
positive control	182.66±2.65	228.70±17.8
Gold nanoparticles 3.75 cm ³	140.00±3.30	201.32±7.58
Gold nanoparticles 5 cm ³	149.51±7.94	193.30±19.1
Statistical analysis	F-Value = 3.08** P-Value = 0.011	F-Value = 2.94* P-Value = 0.025

The mark ** indicates the presence of significant differences at the level of $P \leq 0.01$

The mark * indicates the presence of significant differences at the level of $P \leq 0.05$

These results are consistent with the study (Al-Duri, 2022) conducted on the *Cryptosporidium* spp parasite in Tikrit, which recorded an increase in the level of interleukin-1, and also consistent with (Kabu et al., 2023), which recorded an increase in the level of IL-1 β in calves infected with amoebiasis compared to the control group.

The reason for the increase in interleukin-1 (IL-1) in rats infected with the parasite *Amoeba histolytica* is due to several reasons related to the inflammatory response caused by this parasite, including: stimulating the inflammatory response, as the parasite causes severe inflammation in the intestinal tissues due to its

toxic and destructive effect on the tissues, and interleukin-1 is major in the inflammatory response, and is usually secreted by immune cells such as macrophages and lymphocytes in response to tissue injury. Studies have indicated that IL-1 plays a major role in the inflammatory response to amoeba, as it helps stimulate the inflammatory reaction in the infected tissues.

The decreased levels of interleukin-1 (IL-1) in rats infected with the parasite and treated with gold nanoparticles may be because gold nanoparticles can affect the immune system by reducing the secretion of inflammatory cytokines including IL-1. These particles may reduce inflammatory activity by reducing the stimulation of immune cells or inhibiting the excessive secretion of cytokines that contribute to the inflammatory response. Gold nanoparticles may also affect the activity of immune cells such as macrophages and lymphocytes that secrete IL-1. They can reduce the activity of these cells or modify their response, leading to decreased levels of IL-1.

As for the level of interleukin-17, our results agree with (Aboqader et al., 2019), who recorded an increase in the level of interleukin-17 (93.59 ± 25.40) in the group of patients infected with *E. histolytica* compared to its levels in the control group (55.48 ± 18.62), and also agree with what was reached by (Mohammed et al., 2022) in determining the prevalence of amoebic infection in Sulaymaniyah Governorate and measuring some immune parameters among children infected with amoeba, which recorded a slight increase in the level of interleukin-17 (15.24 ± 2.60) in the group of patients infected with *E. histolytica* compared to its levels in the control group (14.78 ± 2.84), and also agree with (Hadi et al., 2022), who recorded high levels of IL-17 in patients infected with the *Giardia* parasite in Dhi Qar Governorate for the third age group Of the patients (6-10 years), with a level of 1184.9 ± 272.3 ng/ml, and in the third age group of the control group, with a level of 389.49 ± 77.13 ng/ml.

It differs from what was recorded by (Habeeb & Abed ., 2021), which recorded a lower concentration of interleukin-17 in patients with intestinal protozoan infection (30.114 ± 4.877 ml/pg) compared to the control group (35.665 ± 3.198 ml/pg).

Interleukin-17 promotes the recruitment of neutrophils to infected areas by stimulating endothelial cells to secrete chemokines such as IL-8 and CXCL1. Neutrophils are immune cells that participate in combating infection by engulfing microbes and secreting enzymes and toxins that kill pathogens, and stimulates immune cells and epithelial cells to produce cytokines and chemokines that contribute to enhancing the inflammatory response. Among these chemokines, IL-6, TNF- α , and IL-1 β play a role in promoting inflammation and the body's response to infection, and IL-17 enhances the ability of dendritic cells to present microbial antigens and stimulate T lymphocytes (T cells). Dendritic cells play an important role in activating T cells and coordinating the immune response, and IL-17 may influence Th1 T cell responses by stimulating the secretion of cytokines that enhance cellular immune activity, helping to fight infection more effectively (Hadi et al., 2022).

The decreased levels of interleukin-17 (IL-17) in rats infected with the parasite *Amoeba histolytica* and treated with gold nanoparticles may be due to the effects of gold nanoparticles on the immune and inflammatory response.

4-Conclusions:

1. Infection with the amoeba parasite leads to the generation of an immune response and thus an increase in defense by the cells that produce cytokines and thus the concentrations of cellular kinetics increase represented by an increase in interleukin-1 and interleukin-17.
2. Nanotechnology has paved the way for the potential of laboratory experiments to use them as drugs to treat parasites.
3. The effect of gold nanoparticles is clear for their use as a treatment for parasites.

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